

DAMAGE INITIATION IN MULTI-FIBER CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS UNDER TRANSVERSE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Cruciform shaped tensile specimens were developed several years ago to negate the free edge singularities that dominate the transverse failure of typical rectangular shaped specimens. The cross-shaped cruciform design has been used primarily with single fiber specimens to estimate the strength and toughness of the fiber-matrix interface. The present work involves the detection of failure initiation in a model multi-fiber unidirectional composite material loaded transverse to the fiber direction. Various failure mechanisms, from fiber debonding to cavitation induced brittle failure of the matrix have been proposed to model the transverse failure of the composite material. In this work a model composite system consisting of two transparent epoxy systems, a brittle 828/D230 RT-cured epoxy system and an 862/W HT-cured epoxy system, with stainless steel fibers having a 0.3556mm diameter are employed in a cruciform shape. The fiber configuration consists of a 5-fiber arrangement in which a fiber is placed at the intersection of the face diagonals of the four remaining fibers located at the corners of a square. Different failure mechanisms can initiate depending on the local stress state influenced by the matrix constraint as the fiber spacing is made to vary. The transparent model composite system allows for in-situ observation of the failure mechanism and the effects of fiber spacing and arrangement on the failure behavior. Micromechanical models are constructed using the finite element method to analyze the stress fields under transverse loading. Parametric studies will be conducted to examine the influence of fiber spacing and arrangement on the stress concentration at the fiber/matrix interface and in the matrix in the vicinity of the interface.

INTRODUCTION

The object of this study is to investigate the failure initiation mechanism of unidirectional composite materials loaded transverse to the fiber direction. From a literature review of past work two competing mechanisms, cavitation induced matrix cracking and fiber-matrix debonding, are responsible for the damage initiation event [1,2]. Also, the quality of the fiber-matrix interface, i.e., a strong or weak interface, can cause a shift in the competing mechanisms. In previous work fiber-matrix debonding has been observed for single fiber cruciform specimens in transparent and semi-transparent matrices by the reflected light method [3,4]. However, multi-fiber cruciform specimens have been limited to metal matrix composites making observation of debond initiation impossible.

The approach for this investigation employs a model composite system consisting of stainless steel wires and two transparent epoxy systems in a cruciform specimen shape. The model composite system allows us to observe the failure initiation as the specimens are loaded transverse to the fiber. It also allows us to vary the spacing of the fibers to observe the change in failure mechanism. Additionally, the large diameter stainless steel fibers of the model composite system can be placed at predetermined locations

allowing control of the fiber spacing and distribution mitigating the influence of fiber misalignment a common problem in straight-sided specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

The cruciform shaped specimen, shown in Figure 1 nullifies free edge effects, that typically dominate the failure of straight sided specimens, because the cross shape concentrates the stresses in the center of the specimen. The maximum stress concentration factor for the cruciform shape occurs in the interior and the free edge singularity is rendered ineffective because the wings of the specimen carry very little load. Figure 2 shows the stress concentration factor (normal stress in the loading direction normalized by the external applied stress) as a function of distance measured from the center of the specimen for an Al/epoxy composite [5]. Thus, failure is observed to initiate in the central region of the specimen and is devoid of the influence of the free edge stresses at the fiber ends. For this work, the cruciform specimen dimensions are given by $2l = 37.8$ mm, $2h = 5.15$ mm, $2a = 12.8$ mm, $R = 6.35$ mm, $t = 1.87$ mm for $1.95d_f$, 2.53 mm for $2.5d_f$ and 3.64 mm for $6d_f$ spacing, and $2g = 108$ mm (see Figure 1 for nomenclature) based on previous optimization studies [6].

Figure 1: Single-Fiber cruciform specimen geometry

Figure 2: SCF as function of normalized distance from center of sample

For this work the multi-fiber model composite consists of a five-fiber arrangement in which the center fiber is placed at the intersection of the face diagonals of the four remaining fibers located at the corners of a square. Figures 3a and 3b, respectively, show a schematic of the cross section of the fiber end for a multiple fiber and single fiber arrangement in the cruciform specimen. The fiber spacing is defined as the center-to-center distance of the corner fibers. In this investigation cruciform specimens having a fiber spacing of $6d_f$, $2.5d_f$, and $1.95d_f$ where considered, where d_f is the fiber diameter.

Transparent matrix materials used for this investigation are an Epon 828 epoxy and an Epon 862 epoxy. The 828 epoxy uses 35% by weight Jeffamine D-230 curing agent. It cures in approximately seven days at room temperature, and has a linear elastic response to loading. The Epon 862 uses Epi-Cure curing agent W in a 79.4% 862 to 20.6% W ratio. This epoxy system has a high temperature curing cycle of 121.1°C at 2 hours and 176.7°C for two hours and has a nonlinear response to loading.

The fibers used in the model composite system are isotropic stainless steel wires having a diameter of 0.3556 mm. The stainless steel wires are large enough to handle for precise placement in the specimen to control fiber arrangement and thus emulate resin rich/fiber rich areas common to commercially produced composites. They also reflect light well enabling the use of the reflected light method [3] to capture the debond initiation and quite possible, the cavitation of the matrix at or near the fiber-matrix interface. They also are known to bond to the resins being used in this work without the use of any surface treatments or sizings.

The cruciform specimens are made from a silicone rubber mold formed from an aluminum blank having the dimensions listed above. Stainless steel fibers are threaded through two aluminum fiber templates, made by drilling 0.3556 mm diameter holes in the 5-fiber arrangement, as shown in Figure 3a, at three different fiber spacings of $6d_f$, $2.5d_f$, and $1.95d_f$. Epoxy matrix is carefully placed in the molds and upon completion of the curing cycle the specimens are removed and machined to a uniform thickness and polished to achieve the transparency needed to observe the failure initiation. Glass fiber reinforced tabs are then bonded to each specimen.

The experimental approach uses the reflected light method [6] to observe failure initiation in the model composite specimen as they are loaded to failure. The reflected light method utilizes the change in light reflected off the surface of the fiber, in the case of fiber-matrix debond, or off the surface of a micro-crack or cavitation, in the case of matrix failure, for initial damage detection. This method used in conjunction with high power video microscopes allows in-situ observation of the damage initiation and growth [3]. All specimens tested are video taped to capture the failure initiation and subsequent damage growth to complete fracture of the specimen.

Since changes in the fiber spacing will change the failure initiation location due to changes in the stress distribution around the fiber and also from interaction with its nearest neighbors multiple video cameras are utilized to view different areas of the specimen. Consequently, with this experimental set up, the location of failure initiation for all spatial distributions is captured.

A through frame-by-frame review of the video with respect to time relates the failure initiation to loading. Since all tests are video taped to failure and the testing equipment captures the loading and time histories, the complete load history of each specimen is known. From the instant of complete fracture the time is measured back to the instant of failure initiation detection thus, the load at failure initiation is determined.

Figure 3: Schematic cross-section cruciform wing for (a) multi-fiber and (b) single fiber arrangement

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Our initial effort is focused on examining the influence of fiber spacing in initiating failure. As previously mentioned, three fiber spacings, namely, $6d_f$, $2.5d_f$ and $1.95d_f$, representing isolated, closely packed and densely packed fiber distribution arranged in a five fiber pattern shown in Fig 3a were tested for this

study. In addition, single fiber specimens in both matrices were also tested to compare their behavior with multi-fiber specimens having large fiber spacings.

Three single-fiber specimens in 828 Epoxy and five single-fiber specimens in 862 epoxy matrix were tested. In all cases, fiber-matrix debonding is the observed failure initiation mode. The debond initiates in the central portion of the specimen at the interface in the loading direction and propagates axially along the fiber length with an increase in external stress level. Also, the debond grows circumferentially around the fiber with increasing load before branching out into the matrix. Table 1 lists the far-field applied stress levels at debond initiation for single fiber specimens. The average far-field stress for debonding the fiber-matrix interface in single fiber specimens is 26.15 MPa and 17.93 MPa, respectively, in 828 and 862 Epoxy matrix. Figure 5 shows a photomicrograph of the debonded fiber-matrix interface for a single fiber specimen in 828 Epoxy matrix.

828 Matrix		862 Matrix	
Specimen	Far-field stress (MPa)	Specimen	Far-field stress (MPa)
A	25.99	A	18.08
B	26.20	B	23.56
C	26.27	D	14.56
		E	16.62
		F	16.81

Table 1: Far-field applied stress at debond initiation in single fiber model composites.

Figure 4: Single-fiber model composite specimen showing fiber-matrix debond

Figure 5: Photomicrograph of 1.95df fiber spacing model composite in an unloaded state

Table 2 lists the far-field applied stress at failure initiation for multi-fiber specimens having a fiber spacing of $6d_f$ in 828 and 862 epoxy matrices. The stress values entered in different columns in Tables 2-4 are the far-field values at which the debond is first observed to initiate in the corresponding fiber. It should be further noted that for multi-fiber model composites, multiple interfaces associated with 5 different fibers can now debond either simultaneously or with an increase in loading. Five specimens in 828 Epoxy matrix and six specimens in 862-epoxy matrix were tested with $6d_f$ fiber spacing. In each case for the 828-matrix specimens, failure initiates as a fiber matrix debond. In three out of the five 828 matrix specimens tested, debonding initiates at a point on the interface in the loading direction in either the top or bottom fiber, whereas the central fiber debonds for the remaining two cases. For the 862 matrix specimens, fiber matrix debonding is observed as the failure initiation event in three of the six specimens tested. Like the 828 matrix specimens, failure initiates at the interface in the loading direction. All three fibers, namely, top, center and bottom, debond once each time. No interface debonding or matrix cavitation is observed in the remaining three 862 matrix specimens prior to failure. However, all three of these remaining specimens fail along the interface of the bottom fiber, exposing the fiber surface on failure. The average debond far-field stress for the 828 matrix specimens is 14.47 MPa, whereas, for the 862 matrix specimens it is 25.59 MPa.

828 Matrix	Far-field stress at debond initiation (MPa)			862 Matrix	Far-field stress at debond initiation (MPa)		
Specimen	Top Fiber	Center Fiber	Bott. Fiber	Specimen	Top Fiber	Center Fiber	Bott. Fiber
A	15.58	13.86	19.82	C	-	27.70	-
B	-	18.49	-	E	-	-	27.44
C	-	14.24	12.85	F	21.62	-	-
D	18.56	14.64	-				
E	14.92	14.70	12.49				

Table 2: Far-field applied stress at debond initiation in multi-fiber specimens having $6d_f$ fiber spacing.

Multi-fiber specimens having $2.5d_f$ fiber spacing in 828 epoxy and 862 epoxy are also tested. All three of 828 matrix specimens tested are observed to debond first and the failure initiates in the loading direction at the interface of the bottom fiber. Of the eight 862 matrix specimens tested, 3 exhibit interface debonding in the loading direction, and in each specimen the damage initiates on a different fiber. Of the remaining five 862 specimens, three fail along the fiber-matrix interface exposing the fiber surface on failure, while the remaining two fail in the tab region. No fiber-matrix interface debonding or matrix cavitation was observed in these five remaining 862 specimens prior to failure. Table 3 lists the far-field applied stress at failure initiation in multi-fiber specimens having a $2.5d_f$ fiber spacing. The average far-field stress at debond initiation for the 828 matrix is 16.28 MPa, whereas, for the 862 matrix the average far-field stress at debond initiation is 32.48 MPa.

828 Matrix	Far-field stress at debond initiation (MPa)			862 Matrix	Far-field stress at debond initiation (MPa)		
Specimen	Top Fiber	Center Fiber	Bott. Fiber	Specimen	Top Fiber	Center Fiber	Bott. Fiber
A	-	-	15.16	C	30.19	-	-
B	-	-	16.51	D	-	31.12	-
C	19.04	20.13	17.18	E	-	-	36.13

Table 3: Far-field applied stress at debond initiation in multi-fiber specimens having a $2.5d_f$ fiber spacing.

Five specimens are tested with the smallest fiber spacing equivalent to $1.95d_f$ in 828 Epoxy matrix. Unlike the single-fiber composites and multiple-fiber composites with $6d_f$ and $2.5d_f$ fiber spacings, the fiber-matrix interface does not debond first in majority of the composites tested. Instead damage initiates mainly in the form of matrix cavitation in four out of five specimens tested and appears as white spots in the matrix on the video screen. Figure 5 and 6(a) are photomicrographs of a multi-fiber composite with $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing when unloaded and at a far-field stress of 11.04 MPa, respectively. The development of white spots in the matrix due to cavitation is clearly seen, as marked in Figure 6(a). Subsequently, the fiber-matrix interface also debonds on increasing the applied load, as seen in Figure 6(b). Table 4 lists the far-field stress at which damage initiates as matrix cavitation and the stress levels at which the fiber-matrix interface debonds in multi-fiber composites with $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing in Epoxy 828 matrix. The average stress values for matrix cavitation and fiber-matrix debonding for multi-fiber composites with $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing are 6.22 MPa and 11.00 MPa, respectively.

828 Matrix	Far-field stress at debond initiation (MPa)			
Specimen	Far-field stress at Cavitation	Top Fiber	Center Fiber	Bottom Fiber
C	-	-	-	9.09
D	2.90	-	7.65	8.67
E	2.77	-	5.20	6.01
F	10.60	18.61	18.61	-
G	8.60	14.47	14.47	14.83

Table 4: Far-field applied stress at damage initiation in multi-fiber specimens with $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing.

Figure 6: Photomicrograph of $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing model composite under (a) an applied far-field stress of 11.04 MPa and under (b) an applied far-field stress of 23.24 MPa.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS

A preliminary 2-D finite element analysis (FEA) of the cross-section of the fiber end is done using the ABAQUS [8] code. Both single and multiple fiber cruciform specimens are analyzed. The 2-D analysis is done as a prelude to the full 3-D analysis of the cruciform geometry to guide the experimental effort in terms of identifying regions of interest where failure is likely to initiate as the fiber spacing is varied. The models are simplified by using symmetry planes so that a quarter of the cross sectional area is required to be modeled as shown in Figure 7.

The planes of symmetry, namely at $X = 0$ and $Y = 0$, are constrained by symmetry boundary conditions, whereas the outer surface is traction free. The FEM is loaded by applying tension perpendicular to the fiber axis by means of constant displacement of the end nodes to simulate clamped-end conditions. The steel reinforcement and epoxy matrix are modeled with 8 noded quadrilateral solid elements [QUAD8] with the elastic properties listed in Table 5. The fiber-matrix interface is assumed to be perfectly bonded since the stress distribution in the sample is examined prior to damage. Finer subdivisions are employed in the regions where the stress gradient is expected to be high, such as along the fiber-matrix interface.

Figure 7: 2-D FEM of model of multi-fiber composite showing mesh density (θ measured CCW from loading direction).

Material	Young's Modulus	Poisson's Ratio
Stainless Steel	207 GPa	0.30
828 Epoxy	3.44 GPa	0.35

Table 5: Elastic properties of constituent materials used in Finite Element Analysis.

Figure 8 shows the variation of the radial stress at the fiber matrix interface normalized by the far-field stress for (a) the center fiber and (b) the corner fiber. The results are shown for single fiber model composites and multi-fiber model composites having fiber spacings of $1.42d_f$, $1.44d_f$, $1.46d_f$, $1.6d_f$, $1.95d_f$, and $6d_f$. At the largest spacing ($6d_f$), the radial SCF for the center fiber is tensile and maximum in the loading direction, i.e., at $\theta = 0^\circ$, and is compressive at $\theta = 90^\circ$. With a smaller fiber spacing ($1.95d_f$), the stress distribution tends to become more uniform along the circumference as the radial SCF reduces at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and increases at $\theta = 90^\circ$. However, with further decrease in spacing, the radial SCF begins to peak at $\theta \sim 45^\circ$, as the central fiber begins to feel the interaction effect of the neighboring fibers. Note that with reduction in fiber spacing, the fibers approach each other along the square diagonal (i.e., $\theta = 45^\circ$), and at the smallest fiber spacing equal to $1.42d_f$ the fibers are almost on the verge of touching each other. Moreover, the magnitude of the radial SCF is higher at $\theta = 90^\circ$ compared to the value at $\theta = 0^\circ$ for the model composites having a fiber spacing of $1.6d_f$ and smaller. This behavior is reflective of the influence of the fiber spacing on the fiber-matrix interface.

The radial stress distribution for the corner fiber is identical to the behavior of the radial stress for central fiber at $6d_f$ spacing. Thus, at this fiber spacing, there are no interaction effects from the neighboring fibers and both the central and corner fibers behave as if they are isolated. For the corner fiber, the radial stress is tensile at $\theta = 180^\circ$ and becomes compressive at $\theta = 270^\circ$ for $6d_f$ spacing. As the fiber spacing is reduced, the magnitude of the radial SCF is seen to decrease at $\theta = 180^\circ$, but still remains tensile. On the other hand, the radial stress at $\theta = 270^\circ$ remains compressive for all fiber spacings examined. This behavior, at $\theta = 270^\circ$, is somewhat expected since this location is normal to the loading direction. Similar to the center fiber, the radial stress at the interface for the corner fiber begins to peak at the point where the distance between the fibers is the shortest, i.e., at $\theta \sim 225^\circ$, as the spacing is reduced below $1.6d_f$. Thus, interaction effects begin to dominate the stress distributions at smaller fiber spacings.

Figure 8: Variation of the Radial Stress Concentration Factor for (a) center fiber and (b) corner fiber.

The behavior of the shear stress at the interface is shown in Fig 9a and 9b for the center and corner fiber, respectively. For the center fiber, the shear stress is zero at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° , and exhibits a peak at θ

$= 45^\circ$. Further, the magnitude of this peak is seen to increase with decreasing fiber spacing, for fiber spacing less than $1.95d_f$. The shear stress distribution for the corner fiber behaves in a manner similar to the center fiber, except for one major difference. The shear stress is zero at $\theta = 180^\circ$ and $\theta = 270^\circ$ for $6d_f$ spacing, i.e., when the fibers are apart. However, as the spacing is reduced, non-zero shear stresses develop at these locations, i.e., at $\theta = 180^\circ$ and $\theta = 270^\circ$, possibly due to interaction with the stress field of the neighboring fibers.

Figure 9: Variation of the Shear Stress Concentration Factor for (a) center fiber and (b) corner fiber.

Fig 10a and 10b show the variation in hoop stress in the matrix at the interface for the center and corner fiber, respectively. These stress components are observed to behave in a manner very similar to their corresponding interfacial radial stresses with respect to variations in fiber spacing. Similar to the radial and shear stresses at the interface, the maximum hoop stress in the matrix at the interface also occurs at the point on the fiber-matrix interface where the distance between the fibers is the shortest, as the fiber spacing is reduced below $1.6d_f$. In all cases examined, the magnitude of the hoop stress in the matrix is lower than the corresponding radial and shear stresses at the interface.

Figure 10: Variation of the Hoop Stress Concentration Factor for (a) center fiber and (b) corner fiber.

Finally, note that the SCF at the interface for the multi-fiber model composite having a fiber spacing of $6d_f$ has close agreement with the single-fiber model composite for all three-stress components in all cases analyzed above. It appears that at this particular spacing (and beyond), the fibers see no influence of the neighboring fibers. Consequently they act as if they were isolated, whereas the closer spaced model composites see the influence from their neighboring fibers.

DISCUSSION

This study investigates single and multi-fiber model composites having fiber spacing equivalent to isolated and closely packed configurations under loading transverse to the fiber direction in two matrix systems. For the model composites having the wide fiber spacing of $6d_f$ and $2.5d_f$ the predominate failure initiation event is fiber-matrix debonding in both matrix systems. However, for the model composites having the close fiber spacing of $1.95d_f$ in the 828 matrix system, the predominate failure initiation event is cavitation of the matrix. We have not tested composites with $1.95d_f$ fiber spacing in 862-epoxy matrix, as yet.

A preliminary 2-D finite element analysis is done to investigate the influence of fiber spacing on the stress field distribution. It is seen that the stress fields of the neighboring fibers begin to interact as fiber spacing becomes less than $1.6d_f$. The manifestation of the interaction is seen as a peak in the stress concentration factor for the radial, shear and matrix hoop stress components at the points on the fiber-matrix interface where the distance between the fibers is the shortest. The 2-D analysis reveals that at the larger fiber spacing ($6d_f$), the center and the corner fibers have identical stress distributions and behave as if they are isolated, since the multi-fiber results at $6d_f$ spacing are in close agreement with the single fiber solutions. Thus, there is no specific fiber preference for debonding, i.e., all three fibers, namely, top, center and bottom, have an equal probability to debond at the wider fiber spacing. In our experiments, debonding initiates randomly at all three fiber locations in different composite specimens. However, the average far-field stress at which failure initiates in multi-fiber specimens at $6d_f$ spacing differs considerably from their respective single-fiber values in both matrix systems. Obviously, the 2-D analytical results obtained for this work are not supportive of the measured trends in far-field stress values. Likewise, for 828 Epoxy matrix, the average far-field stress causing debond initiation is observed to decrease with decreasing fiber spacing (from 6 to $2.5d_f$), whereas, it increases for Epoxy 862 matrix. This behavior too cannot be explained by the results of the present analysis, since the elastic response of 828 Epoxy and 862 Epoxy do not differ significantly at the stress levels under consideration. Finally, there is a distinctive change in failure initiation mode in multi-fiber Epoxy 828 specimens as the fiber spacing is reduced from larger spacing (6 and $2.5d_f$) to a smaller spacing ($1.95d_f$). However, the values of the radial, shear and matrix hoop stress concentration factors, examined in this work, reflect small changes in the stress distributions for these fiber spacings. There is probably a greater interaction of the neighboring stress field than given by the 2-D results, and therefore, the use of maximum stress as a failure criteria is probably not appropriate.

A three-dimensional stress state exists in the central region of the multi-fiber cruciform specimen under transverse loading. With decrease in fiber spacing, the stress fields between neighboring fibers begin to interact. Consequently, a full 3-D analysis of the multi-fiber cruciform geometry is needed to properly relate to the observed damage initiation events. An appropriate failure criterion that involves a combination of the interfacial stress components is needed to relate the observed failure initiation to the measured far-field stresses. Further, as seen in the preliminary 2-D analysis, the location of failure initiation at the interface is also very important. As the fiber spacing decreases below a limiting value, the magnitude of SCF increases and peaks at the point where the distance between the fibers is the shortest showing an interaction of the stress components.

Future work is currently underway to develop a micromechanics based failure criteria to completely understand the transverse failure initiation phenomenon using 3-D analysis of multi-fiber specimens in cruciform geometry. We have also neglected the influence of matrix shrinkage and build up of residual stresses due to curing at high temperature (for 862 Epoxy matrix) for present 2-D analysis. The matrix materials were modeled as linearly elastic. However, the stress-strain response of 862 Epoxy matrix is non-linear. Full characterization of the material system are being undertaken to determine the effects of temperature and moisture on the constitutive and composite behavior. In addition, efforts will be on studying the effects of different fiber arrangements to emulate resin rich/fiber rich areas commonly found in commercially produced composites.

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